

Complexing Behaviour of 5-(*o*)-Chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione with Cu(I), Ag(I), Zn(II), Fe(III), Co(II) and Ni(II)

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Complexes of Cu(I), Ag(I), Zn(II), Fe(III), Co(II) and Ni(II) with 5-(*o*)-chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione have been prepared and characterized on the basis of infrared, electronic spectra, magnetic susceptibility and analytical data.

SOME 5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione ligands(I) have been reported to be biologically active^{1,2}. Though the preparation of 5-(*o*)-chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione(II) has been reported by Srinivasan *et al*³, the complexing behaviour and biological activity of this ligand has not been reported so far. This paper reports the synthesis of the complexes of 5-(*o*)-chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione with Cu(I), Ag(I), Zn(II), Fe(III), Co(II) and Ni(II) ions. The complexes have been characterized with the help of spectral (uv, visible and ir) and magnetic data.

(I)

Experimental

All reagents used were of AnalaR or chemically pure grade.

Preparation of 5-(*o*)-chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione : 5-(*o*)-chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione (here after referred as COTh) was prepared by the literature method³.

Preparation of metal complexes :

(a) **5-(*O*)-chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thionato Cu(I), Ag(I) and Zn(II) :** An aqueous solution of copper acetate (0.5 g, 2.5 m mole), silvernitrate (0.5 g) or ethanolic solution of zinc acetate (0.5 g, 2.8 m mole) was mixed with hot ethanolic (20 cm³) solution of ligand (0.5 g, 2.4 m mole) with continuous stirring when a greenish, white or white solid respectively was obtained. This was washed several times with water and then with hot ethanol to remove the unreacted ligand. The solid was then dried in desiccator at room temperature.

(b) **Tris-5-(*o*)-chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thionato Fe(III) :** A mixture of ferric chloride (0.5 g, 3 m mole), ligand (0.5 g, 2.4 m mole) and sodium acetate (0.7 g) was refluxed for 5 hrs on a water bath when a redish brown solid separated. It was filtered, washed several times with water and hot alcohol and dried in desiccator at room temperature. Similarly, the complexes of cobalt [with cobalt(II) chloride] and nickel [with nickel(II) chloride] were prepared.

Analyses : The analyses of the metal ions and sulfur were carried out by the reported methods^{4,5}. C, H and N analyses were performed by the B.H.U., Varanasi. The results are given in Table 1.

All the complexes were heated at 120° for 4 hrs in oven but no change of colour or loss of weight was observed. IR spectra of the ligand and complexes were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer model 621 using KBr pellets in the 4000-400 cm⁻¹ range. Magnetic susceptibility of the complexes were measured with the help of Faraday balance at room temperature using ferrous ammonium sulphate as standard. Electronic spectra of the complexes and ligand were obtained using nujol mull in the 200-1200 nm range in a Carry 14 recording spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

In solution, the ligand may exist both in the thione(II) and the thiol(III) forms during the reaction. However, due to the presence of the band due to $\nu_{(N-H)}$ and the absence of $\nu_{(SH)}$ band in the ir spectrum of the ligand, the thione form (II) of the ligand is assumed in our studies.

(II)

(III)

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR THE 5-(o) CHLOROPHENYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLE-2-THIONE METAL COMPLEXES

Complex (a)	Colour	C	Found/(Calcd.)%		S	M
			H	N		
FeL ₃	Redish brown	41.5 (41.7)	1.5 (1.7)	12.3 (12.2)	14.0 (13.9)	8.2 (8.1)
CoL ₂	Dark blue	39.6 (39.8)	1.8 (1.7)	11.7 (11.6)	13.4 (13.3)	12.4 (12.2)
NiL ₂	Green	39.7 (39.9)	1.9 (1.7)	11.5 (11.6)	13.5 (13.3)	12.4 (12.2)
CuL	Dark green	34.6 (34.9)	1.7 (1.5)	10.4 (10.2)	11.3 (11.6)	24.1 (23.2)
AgL	White	30.0 (30.1)	1.5 (1.3)	9.6 (8.8)	9.7 (10.0)	33.6 (33.8)
ZnL ₂	White	39.1 (39.3)	1.5 (1.6)	11.7 (11.5)	13.3 (13.1)	13.5 (13.4)

(a) L=5-(o)-chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.

The analytical data of the complexes indicate that the stoichiometry of the complexes is ML₃, ML₂, or ML. It is evident from the ligand molecule that there could be three bonding sites (a) the thiocarbonyl sulfur atom and (b) the two nitrogen atoms. Since the lone pairs on the oxygen atom present in the oxadiazole ring are involved in the resonating structures of the molecule, it is assumed that it should be very poorly basic in character and therefore will not coordinate with the metal ions. Assuming this, the ligand can behave as monodentate, bidentate or tridentate. In order to know the mode of bonding in the complexes, ir studies of these complexes had been undertaken.

In the spectra of the ligand and the complexes the bands around 1610, 1565, 1480, ... 1170, 1125, 1060, 1030, 950, 775, 930 and 715 cm⁻¹ were found to be common and did not shift from their positions. They have, therefore, been assigned to the skeletal mode of vibration of the 1,2 substituted benzene and the oxadiazole rings⁶. Besides these vibrations, the bands at 3275, 1460, 1335, 1065, 680 and 625 cm⁻¹ were also present in the spectrum of the ligand. Since the ligand has one —HNCS and

one —N—NH group, one should expect the bands due to $\nu_{(NH)}$, $\tau_{(NH)}$ and the thioamide bands I, II, III and IV in the regions 3100, 1500, 1300, 1000 and 700 cm⁻¹. The bands at 3275, 625, 1460, 1335, 1065, 680 and 625 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to $\nu_{(NH)}$, $\tau_{(NH)}$, thioamide bands I, II, III and IV respectively. Undoubtedly, the thioamide bands will not be purely due to $\delta_{(NH)}$, $\nu_{(ON)}$ and $\nu_{(O-S)}$ but they must also be coupled with other fundamental modes of skeletal vibration. However, it has been tacitly assumed that the bands arise due to contributions from $\delta_{(NH)}$, $\nu_{(ON)}$, $\nu_{(O-S)}$ and $\nu_{(N-N)}$. The major contribution from $\delta_{(NH)}$ should be present in the band at 1335 cm⁻¹. Further, the directions of the shifts in the positions of all the bands in the spectra of the complexes are the same. It is, therefore, further assumed that the bonding pattern in the complexes should be similar. The major changes in the position of the bands in the spectra of the complexes as compared to that of the ligand are as follows:

(a) The bands due to $\nu_{(NH)}$ and $\tau_{(NH)}$ are not present in the spectra of the complexes indicating the deprotonation of the —NH groups. This is what one would expect in order to maintain the charge balance in the complexes.

(b) The position of the band at 1335 cm⁻¹ [thioamide band (II)] is shifted to higher wave number (~1350 cm⁻¹). This shows that the contribution of $\delta_{(NH)}$ in the thioamide band becomes zero and the bond order of ν_{C-N} is increased suggesting bonding through thiocarbonyl sulfur.

(c) The thioamide band (IV) having major contribution from $\nu_{(O-S)}$, shifts to 650 cm⁻¹ suggesting further that the metal ion is bonded to sulfur.

(d) A new band appears around 500 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes assigned to coupled vibrations having major contribution from $\nu_{(M-N)} + \nu_{(M-S)}$.

It is, therefore, concluded that the metal ions are bonded through thiocarbonyl sulfur and N of the —HNC=S group is deprotonated. It is difficult

to conclude definitely if nitrogen of the —HNC=S group after deprotonation is also participating in bond formation. However, if in the complexes the ligand molecules take an orientation in such a way that it gives a preferred geometry around the metal

ion, the nitrogen atom of the —NC=S group in that case will be coordinating with the metal ions. Further, all the complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents suggesting the polymeric nature of the complexes. This could only be possible if the ligand is behaving as monodentate towards at least two metal ions.

Magnetic susceptibility and visible spectra : Generally, the range of the magnetic moment of tetrahedral Co(II) complexes is 3.9 B.M. — 4.7 B.M. and that of octahedral complexes is 4.7 B.M. — 5.6 B.M.⁷. The value of magnetic moment (4.08 B.M.) of the complexes studied lies well within the range of tetrahedral complexes. Further, the blue colour of the complex also indicate its tetrahedral

geometry and 4A_2 ground state of Co(II) ion (orbitally non-degenerate).

The orbital contribution in the case of Ni(II) tetrahedral complexes (ground state 3T_1) should be high. The experimental value (3.37 B.M.) of the magnetic moment of the nickel complex suggests its tetrahedral geometry (range for tetrahedral is 3.35 - 4.2 B.M.)⁷. The magnetic moment of the complexes of Fe(III) (ground state ${}^6A_{1g}$) is 5.95 B.M. indicating five unpaired electrons which is well within the range of octahedral Fe(III) complexes⁷. Therefore, an octahedral geometry is assumed around the Fe(III) in the complex.

The stoichiometry of copper complex is Cu(COT). This shows that the oxidation state of copper should be +1 resulting in the diamagnetic behaviour of the complex. However, the slight paramagnetic behaviour of the complex may be due to the presence of a small amount of copper in +2 oxidation state as impurity. Thus, we believe that the ligand reduces Cu(II) to Cu(I) during the course of the reaction and the copper in +1 oxidation state form the complex CuL. The complex of Zn(II) and Ag(I) are diamagnetic as expected.

In octahedral complexes one should expect a band around 400 nm in the complexes of Co(II) and Ni(II)^{7,8}. These are absent in the spectra of the complexes under study, indicating the tetrahedral geometry of this complexes. The electronic spectra of the Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes also show a band around 600 nm showing the transition ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_2$ and ${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^3T_2$ for a tetrahedral geometry. There are intra ligand band of all the complexes around 350 ± 15 nm which may be assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition⁹.

On the basis of the analytical, spectral (uv, visible, ir) and magnetic data the following tentative structures have been assigned to the complexes: Ni(COT)₂, Co(COT)₂ and Zn(COT)₂ - Tetrahedral; Fe(COT)₃ - Octahedral; and Ag(COT) and Cu(COT) - Linear.

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References

1. I. MIR, M. T. SIDDIQUI and A. M. CORIE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 2798.
2. O. KURIHARA, O. TOZABURO, TAKEDA, HIDEO, LTO, HIDEO SALAWA, KEIKO, *Tobokkyakka Diagaku Konkyu Nempo* (Japan), 1970, 17, 43; *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, 75, 1102446r.
3. V. R. SRINIVASAN and T. R. VAKULA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 6, 583.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis" 3rd Ed., Longman Green, London, 1961, pp. 496, 486, 533, 523, 529 and 527.
5. F. G. MANN and B. C. SAUNDERS, "Practical Organic Chemistry", Longman, 1970, p. 500.
6. C. N. R. RAO, "Chemical Applications of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York and London, 1963.
7. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Field", John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1966.
8. C. J. BALLHAUSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory" Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, N. Y., 1966.
9. H. H. JAFFI and O. MILTON, "Theory and Applications of Ultraviolet Spectroscopy", John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1st Ed., 1962.